

Yield, and conventional and isotopic analyses of plant material indicate that grain and straw yields, as well as total N uptake, increased with rate of N application up to 108 kg/ha (see table). All timing and methods of N application — banding in dry soil, point placement 10 cm deep in soil, topdressing 2/3 at 35 d after transplanting (DT) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI) and banding 2/3 in dry soil + 1/3 at PI — gave roughly comparable results. However, point placement was superior. Yields with N broadcast in water before leveling and topdressing 2/3 15 DT and 1/3 at PI were lower.

The % N derived from fertilizer increased as the rate of application increased up to 108 kg N/ha. However, the difference between 72 and 108 kg N/ha was insignificant. Point placement treatment was best, broadcasting N in

Effect of rate, timing, and method of N application on yield and N uptake. Giza, Egypt.

N rate (kg/ha)	Time and method of application	Yield (t/ha)		Total N uptake (kg/ha)	% N derived from fertilizer	Fertilizer N uptake (kg/ha)	Recovery (%)
		Grain	Straw				
—	—	4.7	4.8	68.71	—	—	—
36	Banded in dry soil	6.3	6.8	87.53	7.15	6.26	17.4
72	Banded in dry soil	7.5	9.4	120.69	16.01	19.33	26.9
108	Banded in dry soil	8.7	9.1	128.54	18.19	23.36	21.6
72	Broadcast in water before leveling	6.3	7.9	89.78	7.74	6.94	9.6
72	Point placement 10 cm deep	7.6	9.5	115.17	24.59	28.33	39.4
72	10 DT	—	—	—	—	—	—
72	2/3 banded in dry soil + 1/3 at PI	6.6	8.2	105.28	14.18	14.93	20.7
72	2/3 topdressed 15 DT + 1/3 at PI	6.0	6.2	87.17	14.82	12.92	17.9
72	2/3 topdressed 35 DT + 1/3 at PI	7.3	7.7	105.66	20.51	21.68	30.1
—	LSD 5%	0.9	2.4	21.51	—	5.58	—

water before leveling was least effective.

Amount of fertilizer N taken up by the plant showed similar patterns.

Recovery of fertilizer N ranged from 9.6 to 39.4%. Values for point

placement and topdressing 2/3 at 35 DT and 1/3 at PI were highest, those for the traditional treatment of N broadcast in water before leveling were lowest. ☞

Response of flooded rice to different levels and placement methods of urea and urea supergranule

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The efficiency of urea and urea supergranules (USG) at different N rates and placement methods in flooded lowland transplanted rice was studied during 1982 kharif. Jaya variety 25-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing in 5 × 4-m plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The soil (Beni silty clay loam) classified as Aquic Hapludoll had 8.2 pH, 0.76% organic C, 33 kg available P/ha, and 229 kg available K/ha.

Urea was broadcast and incorporated (B&I) at transplanting and topdressed in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. USG was B&I at transplanting, placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows 10 d after transplanting (DT), and B&I at transplanting and topdressed in splits

Influence of N source, level, and placement method on growth, yield components, and yield. Pantnagar (U. P.) India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	Yield (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)
0 Control	61	157	19.7	1.8	81	2.7	3.4
60 urea B&I, basal	62	167	20.5	2.1	89	3.9	4.5
60 USG B&I, basal	64	186	21.0	2.3	96	3.7	4.6
60 USG deep placed, basal	68	203	21.5	2.5	108	3.9	5.4
60 urea B&I, split	64	181	20.7	2.1	91	3.5	4.0
60 USG B&I, split	66	198	21.2	2.4	102	3.6	4.4
60 USG deep placed, split	67	218	21.7	2.6	113	3.4	4.8
90 urea B&I, basal	68	180	21.6	2.7	116	4.2	5.3
90 USG B&I, basal	71	217	22.5	3.2	135	4.2	5.2
90 USG deep placed, basal	75	229	23.5	3.0	153	4.3	6.3
90 urea B&I, split	70	192	22.0	2.9	125	3.6	4.4
90 USG B&I, split	74	225	23.0	3.4	144	4.1	4.9
90 USG deep placed, split	76	236	24.0	3.8	163	4.1	5.2
120 urea B&I, split	80	250	24.5	4.1	174	4.4	5.1
120 USG deep placed, split	83	265	25.0	4.5	185	4.7	7.4
CD (5%)	3	11	0.3	0.1	5	0.6	0.9

at tillering and panicle initiation. All plots received 40 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 20 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. ZnSO₄ was applied at 2.5 kg/ha.

Based on plant height, USG was superior to urea at all N rates and application methods (see table). Split

placement showed the highest plant height, followed by basal placement and B&I split. Similar results were observed with panicles/m², panicle length, panicle weight, and grain filling. The interaction of N source, rate, and placement method significantly influenced grain and straw yield. ☞